

Rényi wavelet extropy of scaling signals

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Abstract

Recently, wavelet based informations tools are being used for fractals to unveil their complexities and provide more elaborate analyses. In this article, the time-domain definition of Rényi extropy is extended to the wavelet domain and a closed-form expression of this extropy for scaling signals of parameter α is obtained. Based on the theoretical results, wavelet Rényi q -extropy planes are obtained for various q and a range of the fractality parameter and, based on these, a complete characterization of the complexities of fractal signals based on Rényi extropies are obtained. Moreover, potential applications for fractal signal analysis are highlighted and useful relations amongst different wavelet Rényi extropy planes are provided.

Keywords

fractals, entropies, wavelet entropies, Rényi wavelet extropy.

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1. Introduction

Information quantifiers such as Shannon, Tsallis and Rényi entropies are used in a variety of situations in the current literature. For instance, Tsallis entropies have proven to be effective for electroencephalogram (EEG) signal analysis [1], structural damage identification [2] and neuroelectrical signal processing [3, 4]. Entropies have been computed in domains such as time, frequency and currently in the time-scale or wavelet domain. For instance, wavelet entropy [5, 6, 7], wavelet (q, q') -entropies [8] and wavelet Fisher's informations [9, 10] have been applied in a multitude of scientific disciplines to study different phenomena. Wavelet Tsallis entropies, e.g., have been used for general stochastic processes [11], fractal signal classification [12], detection of level-shifts in fractal time series [13] and for the characterization of energy prices [14]. Additional information quantifiers include the so-called Fisher-Shannon information planes [15], the LMC complexity [16] and combinations of them. Recently, the extropy concept has been proposed in the literature. Extropy, according to Lad and co-workers [17], is a complementary dual of information entropy and may provide valuable and complementary information about the complexity of a signal. Tsallis, Rényi and

Ginni entropies have been studied in [18, 19, 20] along with some applications to some theoretical probability functions. Entropies are currently a research hotspot in statistics and it is useful to study its application for fractal signals. In this article, wavelet Rényi extropy of fractal signals is obtained by using a time-scale probability mass function, in a similar way wavelet entropy was computed. Rényi extropy planes are obtained and their characteristics for fractal signals are studied in detail. Furthermore, a complete characterization of their complexities are described and potential applications for fractal signals highlighted. The rest of the article is structured as follows, section 2 briefly overviews wavelets and the wavelet analysis of fractal signals. Important theoretical results on wavelet analysis of fractal signals are highlighted along with definitions that are essential for the understanding of the rest of the article. Later, section 3 presents the main contribution of the article which is the wavelet Rényi q -entropies of fractal signals. In addition, extropy planes are obtained and based on these, a complete characterization of Rényi extropy for fractals is presented. Moreover, potential applications are highlighted in this section. Finally, section 4 presents the conclusions of the paper.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Wavelet analysis of fractals

Wavelets are employed in numerous scientific areas for studying nonstationary and stationary signals [21, 22, 23]. Wavelet transforms can be broadly classified as continuous wavelet transforms (CWT) and discrete wavelet transforms (DWT). The DWT of a signal X_t is defined as:

$$d_X(j, k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} X_t \psi_{j,k}(t) dt, \quad (1)$$

where $\psi_{j,k}(t) = 2^{-j/2} \psi(2^{-j}t - k)$ is a dyadically scaled and integer-translated mother wavelet $\psi(t)$. For fractal signals, the first and second order moments of the DWT are of primary importance. The first moment is obtained as,

$$\mathbb{E}d_X(j, k) = 2^{-j/2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} X(t) \psi(2^{-j}t - k) dt, \quad (2)$$

while, the second moment, also known as the wavelet spectrum [24], takes the form:

$$\mathbb{E}d_X^2(j, k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_X(2^{-j}f) |\Psi(f)|^2 df, \quad (3)$$

where $\Psi(f) = \int \psi(t) e^{-j2\pi ft} dt$ is the Fourier integral of $\psi(t)$, $S_X(\cdot)$ is the power spectral density (PSD) of the process X_t and \mathbb{E} the expectation operator. For fractals, it is well known that the PSD is $S_X(f) \sim c|f|^{-\alpha}$ and thus by substituting this PSD into equation (3) results in the wavelet spectrum of fractals signals of parameter α [24], i.e.,

$$\mathbb{E}d_X^2(j, k) = C2^{j\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

where C is a constant. From equation (4), the wavelet energy at scale j is computed as in [6] and results in,

$$p_j = \frac{\mathbb{E}d_X^2(j, k)}{\sum_j \mathbb{E}d_X^2(j, k)}. \quad (5)$$

Wavelet energy p_j is a pmf and based on this, many statistical quantities can be computed including Rényi entropies. For fractal signals, the wavelet energy, p_j , is given by,

$$p_j = 2^{(j-1)\alpha} \times \frac{1-2^\alpha}{1-2^{\alpha N}}, \quad (6)$$

where α is the fractality parameter and N is the number of scales considered within a signal. For further information on wavelets, the interested reader may refer to [25, 26, 21, 22] and for the analysis and estimation of fractals refer to [27, 28, 29].

2.2 Information theory quantifiers

Entropy measures the information content or uncertainty of a random signal or system. Information quantifiers can be classified in a general sense as extensive or nonextensive. Shannon entropy is a extensive entropy and is appropriate for stationary signals with no correlation structure, short-range forces and which is defined as,

$$\mathcal{H}(p) = - \sum_j p_j \log(p_j), \quad (7)$$

where p_j is a probability mass function (pmf). Rényi entropy, is also extensive but provides an additional parameter q which adds flexibility and the possibility to adjust the analyses with q . It is defined as,

$$\mathcal{H}_q^R(p) = \frac{\log(\sum_{j=1}^N p_j^q)}{1-q}, \quad (8)$$

where $q \neq 1$. Rényi entropies converge to Shannon entropy when $q \rightarrow 1$. Extensive and non-extensive entropies can be further extended if entropies are computed in a different representation of the signal. For instance, when the entropies are computed in a wavelet-based representation of the signal by means of the wavelet spectrum, then wavelet entropies results. Wavelet-based information quantifiers have shown to be appropriate for the analysis of fractal signals [6, 5].

2.3 Rényi extropy

Recently, the concept of extropy has been introduced as a complementary dual of Shannon entropy [17]. Extropy can further complement the analysis based on entropy and provide valuable information in the analysis of a phenomena. For a pmf p_j , extropy is defined as

$$\mathcal{J}(p) = - \sum_j (1-p_j) \log_2(1-p_j). \quad (9)$$

Rényi extropy is a complementary dual of Rényi entropy [19]. Rényi extropy extends the extropy concept by providing an

additional parameter q which adds flexibility in the analyses. Rényi entropy is defined as

$$\mathcal{J}_q^R(p) = \frac{-(N-1) \log(N-1)}{1-q} + \frac{(N-1) \log\left(\sum_{j=1}^N (1-p_j)^q\right)}{1-q}, \quad (10)$$

and when $q \rightarrow 1$, Shannon entropy results. Several other entropy measures have been proposed in the literature, such as Ginni entropy [20] and belief eXtropy[30]. The main result of the present contribution is to obtain the wavelet Rényi entropy for fractal signals of parameter α . As a matter of fact, wavelet Shannon entropy or simply wavelet entropy is obtained by direct application of equation (6) into equation (9) which results in,

$$\mathcal{J}(p) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} \left(\frac{2^\alpha - 1}{1 - 2^{\alpha M}} \right)^n \times \left\{ \frac{1 - 2^\alpha}{1 - 2^{\alpha M}} \frac{1 - 2^{(\alpha + \alpha n)M}}{1 - 2^{(\alpha + \alpha n)}} - \frac{1 - 2^{\alpha n M}}{1 - 2^{\alpha n}} \right\} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) represents wavelet entropy of fractal signals of parameter α and from this result a complete characterization of entropies can be obtained for fractal signals.

3. Results and discussion

Rényi entropies are obtained by direct application of equation (6) into equation (10) which results in,

$$\mathcal{J}_q^R(p) = \left\{ (N-1) \log \left(\sum_{k=0}^q \left(\frac{1 - 2^{\alpha N k}}{1 - 2^{\alpha k}} \right) \left(\frac{2^\alpha - 1}{1 - 2^{\alpha N}} \right)^k \times \binom{q}{k} \right) - (N-1) \log(N-1) \right\} \times \frac{1}{1-q} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) represents the wavelet Rényi entropy for fractal signals of parameter α . When $q \rightarrow 1$, standard wavelet entropy results and equation (11) is obtained. To study the complexities associated with fractals, the Rényi q -entropy planes based on (12) are computed for a range of α and N . Entropy planes would allow to completely characterize complexities of fractal signals by means of Rényi entropies. Figure 1 shows the Rényi information plane (top plot) for fractal signals in the scaling range $\alpha \in (-4, 4)$ and signal lengths from 2^5 to 2^{15} . Note from this plot that Rényi entropies are maximum for $\alpha = 0$ (white noise), increasing for noncorrelated fractals ($\alpha < 0$) and decreasing for correlated ones ($\alpha > 0$). For stationary signals, Rényi entropies are increasing for short-range dependent signals and for stationary long-memory signals, it is decreasing. For nonstationary fractals, Rényi entropies are decreasing. In addition, Rényi entropies for fractals signals are independent of signal length N . Figure 1 displays the Rényi entropy plane for $q = 15$ and a 2D comparison with standard wavelet entropy.

Figure 1. Wavelet Rényi q -entropy plane (top plot) for $q = 15$ in the fractality range $\alpha \in (-4, 4)$ and varying length. Bottom plot displays Wavelet entropies compared: wavelet entropy $\mathcal{J}(p)$ and wavelet Rényi q -entropy $\mathcal{J}_q^R(p)$ ($q = 15$).

From this plot it is easily observed that,

$$\mathcal{J}(p) > \mathcal{J}_q^R(p), \quad (13)$$

In addition, for different values of the extensivity parameter q , namely, q_1 and q_2 , is verified that the following holds,

$$\mathcal{J}_{q_1}^R(p) > \mathcal{J}_{q_2}^R(p), \quad \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (14)$$

for all $q_1 < q_2$ and $q_1, q_2 > 1$. In fact, a more detailed and complementary study is shown in figure 2 for $0 < q < 1$ and $q > 1$. When parameter $0 < q < 1$ (top plot of figure 2), as q decreases, then Rényi entropies are higher, i.e., as long as $0 < q_1 < q_2 < 1$, then,

$$\mathcal{J}_{q_1}^R(p) > \mathcal{J}_{q_2}^R(p), \quad \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (15)$$

The above behaviour is also observed when $q > 1$ (bottom plot of figure 2), therefore, the higher the q , the thinner the Rényi entropy plane. This behaviour is important since it allows to highlight potential applications to wavelet Rényi entropies. Wavelet Rényi q -entropies do not have constant

regions of extropies in some fractality range for a given value of the parameter q as observed for instance in wavelet Tsallis entropies. This result is similar as those observed

Figure 2. Rényi extropies for different values of the parameter q . Top plot shows the case when $0 < q < 1$. Note that as q increases, then the extropies are thinner. Bottom plot shows the case when $q > 1$. As in the previous case, as q increases, then the Rényi extropies become thinner. This behavior is important since an application for fractal signal classification may be set up with this behaviour.

for standard wavelet q -entropies where the only entropy with constant regions is the wavelet Tsallis entropy. Accordingly, few applications of wavelet Rényi q -extropies can be mapped to fractal signals, however, it is a good descriptor of the complexities associated to fractal signals.

3.1 Classification of fractals

As stated above due to the nature of the wavelet Rényi q -extropies, few applications can be mapped to the analysis of fractals, however, an example application of wavelet Rényi extropies can be in the detection of signals approaching $\alpha \rightarrow 0$. Note that as q increases, the Rényi extropies approach a

pointing arrow towards the $\alpha = 0$ point. This means that if we compute Rényi extropies for fractal signals, then, if the signal is set to $\alpha \neq 0$, most of the extropies will be varying, however when the signal is approaching $\alpha = 0$, then, it is expected according to the theoretical observations that the extropies of the signals will be almost constant with values approaching 1. The above can be an important application since sometimes it is useful to verify the presence or absence of a white noise fractal.

4. Conclusions

In this article, wavelet Rényi q -extropies of fractal signals were obtained by computing standard Rényi q -extropies on a time-scale representation of fractals. Closed-form expressions of wavelet Rényi q -extropies were obtained and based on these, extropy planes were computed. Extropy information planes allowed not only to examine the properties of these extropies but also to study their relationships and the relationship with standard wavelet entropy. Moreover, these planes allowed to highlight an example application of wavelet Rényi q -extropies, specifically in the classification of fractal signals as fractals with $\alpha = 0$.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare there are no conflict of interests regarding this article.

Authors contributions

All authors contribute equally to conceived the idea of the paper and for obtaining the results and the transcription of the paper.

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